

MAIN AREAS OF DIFFICULTIES IN PEDAGOGICAL INTERACTION

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Annotation. The difficulties of one participant in communication affect not only this process itself, the activity of the one who experiences these difficulties, the situation, but also other communication partners, in particular through feedback channels, and the teacher in this situation.

Keywords: communication, teacher, communicative, interactive, cognitive, affective, behavioral, psychological.

Currently, difficulties, or "barriers" to communication are considered from different positions, depending on the basis of their analysis and approach. So, within the framework of general psychological interpretation, they are classified as semantic, emotional, cognitive, tactical. In the activity approach, motivational and operational difficulties are divided, correlated with the two main aspects of communication - communicative and interactive. They, in turn, manifest themselves in the cognitive, affective and behavioral spheres. At the same time, a person's difficulties in communication can be correlated not only with the nature of the activity or emotional, cognitive and other areas of the personality, but also be the result of deeper and at the same time broad influences. The following main areas of human difficulties in communication can be distinguished: ethno-socio-cultural, status-positional-role, age, individual-psychological, activity, area of interpersonal relations. They, of course, overlap, interact with each other in a single integral system "man", but for the purposes of theoretical analysis, the action of each of them can be considered separately.

Difficulties in this area are associated with the peculiarities of ethnic consciousness, values, stereotypes, attitudes of human consciousness, manifested in communication in the specific conditions of its social and cultural development. As a rule, communication difficulties caused by the ethno-socio-cultural characteristics of its subjects are taken by people as a matter of course. At the same time, it is obvious that each subject of activity, communication partner as a carrier of a certain mentality, as a person whose thinking, according to the apt expression of L.V. Shcherba, "cast" in the form of his native language, interacts with other people in accordance with the norms, traditions, image of the world and attitude inherent in the people, of which he is a representative.

This area of difficulty is most often revealed in an insufficiently complete understanding of the very intention of communication, its tone, style. Features of the ethno-socio-cultural area also cause a number of difficulties in observing the etiquette of communication. An important role in this ethno-sociocultural conditionality of communication is played by non-verbal means - facial expressions, gestures, postures, the correct "reading" of which is the key to adequate mutual understanding and mutual action of those communicating. Difficulties in communication, correlated with the ethno-socio-cultural area, can be overcome if their specificity is reflected by the teacher, if he can control his communication, regulating it within the framework of those conventional relations that are assumed by a specific educational system, a specific educational institution.

Status-positional-role area of difficulties. This area of difficulties in communication is due to a number of underlying reasons: family upbringing, position in the community, attributes of the role, status of the institution, educational system, region, city, etc. Such difficulties in communication are most often; arise in conditions of asymmetry of statuses, positions, in situations of violation of the rights and obligations of conventional roles. For example, in a school, the teacher's right to ask about conventional relations implies the obligation of the student to answer. If the student asks a question that the teacher finds it difficult to answer, then, using his right to ask, the teacher can redirect the question, postpone the answer; those. change the course of communication. The unity of the teacher's status as a representative of the school, education, his position - the transmission, translation of social experience and his role - the developing, educating and teaching subject is expressed in the authority of the teacher. Authority combines at least two components: the authority of the individual and the authority of the role.

The age characteristics of communication partners can also cause difficulties. It is known that a child before school prefers communication with adults; up to middle adolescence, almost half of children prefer communication with peers. This preference dominates among high school students until graduation, when again about a third of boys and girls show interest in communicating with adults. Difficulties in communicating with an adult, with a teacher most often arise due to the fact that a student, especially a teenager, believes that his inner world is incomprehensible to adults who continue to address him as if he were a child. Difficulties in communication may arise when the teacher, due to employment or other interests, really does not know the world of music, painting, dance, cinema, the language and values of the youth subculture. In this case, he does not have a common subject of communication with students. The problem of fathers and children in pedagogical communication, as it were, shines through the fabric of role-playing relationships "teacher-student". Overcoming the difficulties of communication associated with the age characteristics of the teacher lies in his constant personal and professional self-development, his inclusion in society, interest in the world of youth. "He who does not burn himself, but smolders, cannot ignite anyone," says ancient wisdom. Difficulties can also arise when, on the contrary, the teacher is younger than his students or listeners. The desire of the teacher in this situation to appear older is expressed in an emphatically business-like manner of communication, inadequate severity of intonation, arbitrariness in the selection of stylistically formal language means, which violates the naturalness of the communication situation, making it difficult to be comfortable.

The individual psychological characteristics of communication partners, both the teacher and students, most often cause communication difficulties. This is explained, firstly, by the fact that these difficulties are the result of the interrelation and interaction of at least three forces: the individual psychological characteristics of the teacher, the student and their acceptance by each other. As E.A. Klimov, the coincidence of individual styles of activity, reflecting the individual psychological characteristics of people, is one of the main conditions for their easy communication. Secondly, this difficulty in pedagogical communication can be explained by the conscious lack of regulation, restraint by the teacher of their individual psychological characteristics that negatively affect communication, such as irritability, excessive emotionality, criticality, skepticism, etc. The situation is aggravated by the fact that it can be

an expression of the position of the teacher, according to which he should be "natural" in his individual, in particular emotional, manifestations.

K. Jung's statement could not fail to attract the attention of investigators and necessitate the study of this problem. According to L.A. Kharaev, that among the students of a pedagogical university and novice teachers, on the contrary, there are quite a lot of introverts. But this does not mean that their pedagogical activity will be unsuccessful or that they should change. Most teachers who have been successfully working for several years are ambiverts, which indicates the influence of the activity itself on the change in individual characteristics. At the same time, studies have shown that extroversion, a positive characteristic of communication, can lead to desynchronization of communication.

To individual psychological factors that cause certain difficulties in communication for both the speaker and the listener; refers to the cognitive style of activity. This is a whole system of features of cognitive, primarily analytical and synthetic activity, features of the organization of semantic memory, the structure of the thesaurus, strategies for choosing means and methods of action and decision-making. Cognitive style, like any other individual style, is a feature of cognitive activity that is steadily manifested in changing situations, and in particular in communicative situations. It is noted that one of the main characteristics of the cognitive style is the degree of differentiation of cognitive structures, picture and image of the world. Two polar cognitive styles are distinguished - with low and high differentiation. Many studies indicate that subjects with low psychological differentiation prefer interpersonal and group activities to individual ones, they are more successful in communication. At the same time, it is shown that people with high differentiation of cognitive structures better understand another person.

Rather big difficulties are caused by a low level of emotional regulation (or its absence in communication), which manifests itself in the uncontrolled reaction of communication partners to each other, to the text, to the entire communicative situation. The stressor can be an activity, a partner, or the speaker himself. Depending on this, the general tone of communication, intonational, lexical and grammatical characteristics of the text, non-verbal means change. Accordingly, it can be said that individual psychological characteristics, including intellectual, affective, volitional, behavioral, personal manifestations, can both facilitate and complicate communication. Everything that causes difficulty in pedagogical communication should be the subject of awareness and correction as a professionally necessary condition for a person to comply with this activity.

Difficulties in communication associated with the very pedagogical activity of the teacher and the educational activity of the student are associated with the content and nature of these activities. In pedagogical activity, difficulties can be caused both by the subject content itself, i.e. the level and nature of the teacher's possession of those knowledge, the organization of the assimilation of which is the basis of his activity, as well as professional and pedagogical skills, didactic competence, i.e. means and methods of pedagogical influence on students. Accordingly, the main directions of pedagogical difficulties are associated with the development itself, the content and forms of the educational process, as well as with the characteristics of the teacher as a subject of training and education, and with the process of communication. Expressed in insufficiently complete and accurate planning of the result of their actions, not taking into account past erroneous actions, insufficient flexibility in

changing and attaching tasks during the lesson, narrowing their content by excluding the educational and developing functions. This leads to the formalization of the lesson, reducing the interest of students. The difficulties of pedagogical influence on the student's personality lie, first of all, in "the inability to see the student as an integral person, who is in the process of formation and development." As a result, the student is not personally involved in communication, which causes a feeling of dissatisfaction and discomfort on both sides. At the same time, A.K. Markova emphasizes that the difficulties of the teacher's teaching activity are also determined by the objective difficulties of combining productive, creative and reproductive forms of work in the educational process, the teacher's inability, and sometimes unwillingness to overcome these difficulties.

V.A. Kan-Kalik, A.K. Markova noted that difficulties in learning activities can be caused, firstly, by the fact that one method used is in no way connected with others; secondly, the teacher uses several methods that are not related to each other; thirdly, the applied teaching method does not correspond to the capabilities of the students; fourthly, it does not correspond to the individual psychological characteristics of the teacher (for example, if an active, impulsive, contact extrovert teacher uses the method of algorithmic, step-by-step control, or if a deep introvert plays a business game in the form of a blitz solution). The difficulties of the third direction are connected with communicative interaction, with communication between the teacher (teacher) and the class (audience). Difficulties in pedagogical communication (especially for novice teachers) were named by V.A. Kan-Kalik by some psychological barriers that, interfering with normal communication, affect all pedagogical and educational activities of all its subjects. Psychological barriers are not always recognized by the teacher himself; accordingly, he does not feel the need to analyze the communicative situation and correct the cause that causes difficulties in communicating with the class. The difficulties of one participant in communication affect not only this process itself, the activity of the one who experiences these difficulties, the situation, but also other communication partners, in particular through feedback channels, and the teacher in this situation. The teacher either overcomes difficulties, continues communication and activities, or, experiencing a feeling of discomfort, creates a new communicative situation and new forms of activity, feeling embarrassed for the lack of preparation, organization, taking into account the characteristics of the communicative situation, or takes an outwardly accusatory position, changing in some cases the adequacy of the assessment of the environment. Reality

In conclusion, we can say that the analysis of the main areas of difficulties in communication, in activity shows that they change the very situation of communication. Opposite goals, interests, positions, means, methods of activity, colliding, create a conflict, which is studied not only by special sections of psychology, but by the whole science of conflictology, to which we refer the interested reader. It should also be noted here that in group interaction, conflict as a clash of opposing decisions, strategies, means and methods, creating a problematic situation, increases the intellectual activity of the aggregate (group) subject. It is only important that such a conflict does not move to the level of evaluation of the subjects themselves and does not become negatively interpersonal in the narrow sense of the word.

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